

MATERIALS SELECTION FOR A FIBER-METAL-LAMINATE WITH ELASTOMER INTERLAYERS

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Keywords: Fiber-Metal-Laminate, Materials selection, Elastomer, CFRP, FMEL

ABSTRACT

Materials selection for a fiber-metal-laminate with elastomer interlayers was carried out. The expected load for the laminate was flexural sheet bending. The laminate was selected to ensure a flexural stiffness, while minimizing the weight of the structure. The selection criteria were applied for the constituents and the laminate design. Restrictions like a symmetrical layup and a laminate thickness of 2.5 mm were enforced during the selection process. The constituent material was selected during the process before the laminate was optimized. The constituent thickness and stacking sequence were optimized with respect to lightweight potential and flexural stiffness. A laminate with carbon fiber reinforced polymer face sheets, aluminium core layer, and elastomer interlayers was found to be the optimal choice under these constraints.

1 INTRODUCTION

Engineers desire to create the perfect component, but often the material, shape and other constraints lead to imperfection. In order to generate the perfect component, the best suited material has to be chosen. However, which material is suited best depends on the load applied to the structure. Therefore, the applied loads throughout the life cycle have to be predicted to minimize security factors due to inaccurate load approximations. Other, secondary objectives are often defined in order to minimize weight or to withstand a high temperature.

The best material cannot be easily chosen when multiple goals are to be reached, thus, a holistic and systematic materials selection has to be conducted. The materials selection process is often carried out to find the optimum in performance, while minimizing weight [1]. For that objective to be achievable, properties of all materials have to be known. In a selection process all materials are taken into account before eliminating unsuitable materials because of their properties. Therefore a database of all materials and their properties is also necessary. In this study CES EduPack from Granta Design Ltd. [2] was used as database.

With dimensions, load and the mechanical properties of a material known, the mechanical performance of a component can be calculated. However, the moment of inertia combined with design possibilities has to be considered, because performance increase or weight reduction can be taken from intelligent design.

The stress in the material and the given constraints (e.g. dimensions, weight or working temperature) can be decisive, whether a material is suited for the application or should be discarded. This process is carried out until only well performing materials are left. Those materials are ranked and the best option is chosen.

In this work a laminate structure for application in the automotive industry was selected. The laminate was expected to feature a fiber-reinforced-polymer (FRP), an elastomer interlayer as well as a metal constituent. Laminates with FRP constituents have already been investigated [3]. However, only glass fibers were found to be suited for the application, so that only GLARE, glass laminate aluminum reinforced epoxy, is commercially manufactured. Carbon fibers would introduce risk of corrosion and delamination due to a mismatch of coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE-mismatch) [4, 5].

In this study the constituents are not predetermined due to previously conducted research, because the elastomer interlayer is desired to solve problems arising from fiber types other than glass fibers.

The laminate was defined to consist of layers of FRP, elastomer and metal. The objective was to maximize the flexural stiffness of the laminate while minimizing the weight. A laminate structure in general was chosen, because fiber-metal-laminates (FML) show a low crack propagation rate combined with low densities and a reasonably high stiffness [6]. A popular FML, GLARE, is already commercially available and shows good mechanical properties. The application is found in aviation.

The objective was, however, to find a FML, possibly with an interlayer, which has the potential to surpass the properties of GLARE [6].

The laminates thickness and the predicted flexural load were predefined. The resulting material index can be optimized with respect to the materials used, the order in which the laminate is stacked and the sheet thicknesses. The resulting material concept is desired to have the maximum flexural stiffness while preserving a low density. Different layups, sheet thicknesses and materials are monitored to find the best laminate.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The FMEL in this study had predefined material classes in the constituents. The free variables in this work were the fiber type, polymer matrix material, elastomer mixture and material of the metal sheet, which were all chosen during the selection process. After the materials were selected, the stacking succession and the constituent thickness were optimized.

2.1 Restrictions to the FMEL and the constituents

A symmetrical laminate was selected to inhibit warpage due to cooling from manufacturing temperature and to ensure dimensional stability through temperature changes [7, 8]. The symmetry resulted in symmetrical flexural properties and ensured better comparability between laminates. Before the flexural properties of the laminate could be determined, the constituents had to be selected. All materials, the constituents and the resulting laminates, were selected according to high flexural stiffness and low density.

Figure 1: 5-layer FMEL specimen

Additionally, between each metal and FRP sheet there needed to be elastomer interlayer. The interlayer inhibited corrosion and balanced the CTE-mismatch due to high strains. Figure 1 shows a symmetrical 5-layer FMEL specimen featuring CFRP face sheets, elastomer interlayers and an aluminum core sheet. The total thickness of the laminate was set to 2.5 mm.

2.1.1 Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP)

The FRP component in FML is non isotropic, which means that the fiber orientation can be matched to the load direction. In this study biaxial fiber orientation was used to calculate the results. The orientation was selected to reduce the chance of warpage of the laminate.

2.1.2 Elastomer interlayer

The elastomer was not expected to contribute to the laminate stiffness. However, the elastomer interlayer had to have good adhesion to the metal sheet and the FRP constituent. Additionally inhibition of corrosion and delamination due to the CTE-mismatch were the objective of the interlayer.

2.1.3 Metal sheet

The metal sheet for the laminate needed to have a low thickness and high mechanical properties combined with a low density.

2.2 Materials selection

The materials selection was carried out according to Ashby et al. [1]. The flexural stiffness was to be increased, while the density had to be minimized. Two equations are therefore necessary. The first equation calculated the mass of the structure using the density and the dimensions of the structure. This equation was used to minimize the weight of the resulting component.

$$m = \rho t l b \quad (1)$$

Here m is the mass of the sheet, ρ is the density, l the length and b the width. All variables are directly related to the material or are dimensional variables. Only the thickness t is a free variable and can be eliminated. The second objective was to increase the flexural stiffness of the component. Therefore the second inequation calculated the stiffness of the structure.

$$S < \frac{CEI}{L^3} \text{ where } I = \frac{bt^3}{12} \quad (2)$$

The maximum applied stiffness S has to be lower than the sheets resistance, which is defined with a constant C , the Young's modulus E , the axial moment of inertia I and the length L . Equation 1 combined with inequation 2 results in the third inequation. The mass of the structure is isolated, so the weight reduction can be connected to the mechanical properties. The middle terms of the inequation feature constants and dimensional variables, which were constant for every material. Only the last term defines the lightweight potential for the laminate. The symbol of inequality already defines the optimization direction.

$$m > \left(\frac{12Sb^2}{C} \right)^{1/3} l \left(\frac{\rho}{E^{1/3}} \right) \quad (3)$$

The last term can be seen as a straight line in a double logarithmic Young's modulus vs. density diagram. As presented in Figure 2 each dash on the slanted dashed line resembles the same lightweight potential. The optimum is found in the top left corner. The optimization calculation was carried out for the constituent materials and subsequently for the laminates with different constituent thicknesses and successions.

3 RESULTS

With the restrictions for the laminate defined, the materials selection could be carried out. A Young's Modulus versus density diagram can be deduced for the constituent materials and for the laminate with the different laminate structures each consisting of one data point. The dashed lines in the diagram resemble the same lightweight potential for specific flexural stiffness. The optimum laminate would be positioned in the top left corner of the diagram.

3.1 Constituents

The constituents chosen for the FMEL were selected according to high specific flexural stiffness. The materials selection diagram is shown in Figure 2, where steel, aluminum and magnesium are highlighted for the metal layer. CFRP and GFRP are labeled for the FRP component. Other material groups are marked as well to show the overall performance of the constituents. The dashed line can be moved to the top left corner to find the optimum. This diagram shows that magnesium would be suited best before aluminum and the least suited material is steel. CFRP is better suited than GFRP. The dashed line in the diagram shows, that a decrease in density is far more favorable than an increase in stiffness. This relation can also be taken from ineqation 3, where the exponent of the stiffness is 1/3.

Figure 2: Young's Modulus versus density diagram for the selection of the constituents with the optimum in the top left corner and a dashed line marking equally suited materials [2]

3.1.1 Fiber reinforced polymer

Carbon fibers had the best stiffness to density ratio, as it is shown in Figure 2, where the CFRP is situated better than the GFRP.

To generate a high stiffness, unidirectional endless fibers were used, contrary to the diagram. The matrix was an epoxy resin. For easy manufacturing a prepreg was chosen, the commercial name is Hexcel M77/42%/UD90/CHS. The minimum layer thickness was 0.1 mm.

3.1.2 Metal layer

Although the materials selection chart in Figure 2 shows, that the magnesium alloys would be superior, magnesium sheets suffer from the strength-differential effect and are not available in thin rolled sheets. Therefore aluminum was preferred. The specific aluminum alloy was chosen based on strength and comparability, as the stiffness and density did not vary between alloys.

Al-2024-T3 in a pre-hardened state was chosen, which was also used in many other FML [6, 7, 8]. Al-5754 was also selected to enhance dynamic properties. To change corrosive properties and the CTE-mismatch a steel sheet, TS-275, was selected. All metals had a minimum thickness of 0.3 mm.

3.1.3 Elastomer interlayer

The elastomer interlayer could not be selected according to specific stiffness, because the elastomer did not contribute significantly to the laminate stiffness. Therefore a low density was selected with a focus on good adhesion properties to aluminum and the epoxy matrix.

Elastomer layers from Kraiburg Holding GmbH und Co. KG were selected. The commercial names were Kraibon SAA9579-52 and SAA9530-70. The minimum thickness was 0.5 mm.

3.2 FMEL

With the constituent materials selected the laminate had to be designed. The restrictions were 2.5 mm overall thickness and an elastomer interlayer in every CFRP-metal interface. The symmetry and minimum constituent thicknesses forced a 5-layer laminate. Only 2 possible layups existed for these restrictions. Either the face sheets consisted of CFRP and the core was a metal sheet or vice versa. The layups are sketched in Figure 3 on the left side.

For both succession orders the lightweight potential could not be calculated without knowledge of the layer thickness. The layer thickness and the distance from the neutral fiber changed the axial moment of inertia and therefore changing the flexural properties.

The laminates consisting of CFRP, each elastomer and any of the three metal sheets were simulated with varying constituent thicknesses, but within the manufacturing restrictions. The succession of the materials in the laminate had an effect on the flexural stiffness and was evaluated as well. Figure 3 shows the materials selection chart for the FMEL with differently colored data points for the laminates depending on the metal used. The aluminum alloys are presented in the same area, while the steel laminates have higher overall stiffness, but also a higher density.

Figure 3: Young's Modulus versus density chart with data points for different FMEL layups [2]

3.2.1 Succession

The layer succession in the laminate is sketched in Figure 3 on the left side. Generally the axial moment of inertia is changed due to the distance from the neutral fiber and therefore changed the flexural properties by changing the succession of the constituents. In Figure 2 it can be seen, that CFRP has a higher lightweight potential compared to the metal sheets. The higher stiffness compared to the aluminum sheet results in the CFRP layer being placed in the outer fiber. The high density of the steel combined with the symmetry prohibits the steel from being in the face layer, because the density would increase too much. For all laminates the CFRP component was to be used as the face sheet to optimize the specific flexural properties.

3.2.2 Layer thickness

The thickness of each constituent could be increased from the minimum value until the maximum overall laminate thickness was reached. This variation changed the flexural properties of the laminate. A laminate was calculated with each possible layer thickness. Every laminate has a density and stiffness, which can be resembled as a dot in a Young's modulus versus density diagram. Through the variation of thickness in a constituent and the resulting position in the diagram combined with the dashed line for lightweight potential an effect of the layer thickness on the lightweight potential could be deduced.

In Figure 3 the laminates are marked by color depending on which metal sheet was used. Arrows are inserted with captions indicating which layer thickness was increased. It can be seen, that an increase in metal thickness, either aluminum or steel, would cause a higher stiffness. However, also a higher density would be obtained. It is depicted that the lightweight potential is reduced, when the metal sheet thickness was increased.

Increasing the elastomer layer did not result in higher specific flexural properties. Decreasing the CFRP and metal thickness, the elastomer thickness would increase. It is clearly visible that the stiffness drastically decreased and the layer thickness should be minimized.

An increase in CFRP thickness caused the laminate to increase stiffness while decreasing density. Since the increase in metal and elastomer thickness decreased the lightweight potential and only the CFRP increased the specific flexural stiffness, the CFRP layer thickness had to be maximized while the other layers had to be minimized.

4 DISCUSSION

The laminate selected through the materials selection process consisted of 0.6 mm face layers, 0.5 mm elastomer interlayers and a 0.3 mm aluminum core. This laminate had maximized CFRP thickness and minimum metal and elastomer thickness. The laminates were the best situated data points in Figure 3. Since the CFRP had the highest stiffness combined with low density, it had to be situated in the outer fiber and the layer had to be maximized.

The alternative aluminum alloy did not change the materials selection, because the stiffness and density did not change. The steel sheet proved to have disadvantages in the laminate, as the constituent selection in Figure 2 already showed lower lightweight potential. If high overall stiffness would be a restriction, the steel laminate could be selected.

Other FML often feature more than 5 layers [6]. However, the other laminates did not need an elastomer interlayer, because glass fibers were used instead of carbon fibers. Using FMEL the fraction of elastomer would increase with the layer number, which would decrease the lightweight potential.

GLARE has a stiffness of 50-60 GPa depending on the type of laminate. The density is approximately 2300 kg/m³. This would result in a data point in Figure 3, where many laminates could surpass GLARE. However, this would only mean better specific flexural stiffness. Other restrictions, which apply to GLARE to be used in aviation, may not have been met with FMEL.

Other laminates with high lightweight potential like CARALL have already been researched. They feature CFRP and aluminum. CARALL lacks the elastomer interlayer presented in this study. The danger of corrosion and delamination due to the CTE-mismatch and poor adhesion was often the research focus [4, 5]. Therefore, the flexural stiffness and materials selection were often neglected.

5 CONCLUSION

A materials selection for a Fiber-Metal-Laminate with elastomer interlayers was carried out. The laminate was optimized according to high flexural stiffness while minimizing the density. Because of the CTE-mismatch and corrosive potential an elastomer interlayer was introduced in every FRP-metal interface. Different restrictions were applied to each constituent. The constituents were selected likewise to the laminate. Elastomers with good adhesive properties and aluminum alloys were selected for the laminate. The succession and thickness of the constituents changed the specific flexural properties by changing the axial moment of inertia. Therefore the constituent succession and thickness in the laminate were optimized as well. The optimum laminate consisted of thick CFRP face layers, thin elastomer interlayers and a thin aluminum core. The laminate showed the possibility to surpass the commercially available GLARE in respect to specific flexural stiffness.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research of this paper is kindly financed by the Baden-Württemberg Stiftung within the project “Faser-Metall-Gummi-Hybridlaminate (FMGL) ein neuartiges, nachhaltiges Werkstoffkonzept für den Fahrzeugleichtbau”, support code MAT0012, which is part of the research program “Rohstoff- und Materialeffizienz in der Produktion”.

The authors kindly thank the Institute for Production Science (wbk) at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) for the production of the laminates. Also we would like to thank the Kraiburg Holding GmbH und Co. KG for the supply of the elastomer.

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